

1 New Fossils of *Mellivora benfieldi* (Mammalia, Carnivora, Mustelidae) from
2 Langebaanweg, ‘E’ Quarry (South Africa, Early Pliocene): Re-Evaluation of the
3 African Neogene Mellivorines

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16 RH: VALENCIANO AND GOVENDER—PLIOCENE *MELLIVORA* FROM
17 LANGEBAANWEG

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26 ABSTRACT—We describe abundant new remains of the medium-sized mustelid
27 *Mellivora benfieldi* from the early Pliocene site of Langebaanweg (South Africa).
28 The specimens are from the Muishond Fontein Pelletal Phosphorite Member
29 (MPPM) and the Langeberg Quartz Sand Member (LQSM). Novel dentognathic –
30 upper dentition, alveolus for m2– and postcranial –humerus, metacarpal V, femur
31 and calcaneus– information is provided. This sample enables us to review the
32 taxonomic status of Mio-Pliocene African mellivorines. *Mellivora benfieldi* is
33 distinguished from the middle-late Miocene ‘*Eomellivora*’ *tugenensis* from
34 Ngorora Kenya by its smaller size, and a M1 protocone messially placed; from the
35 late Miocene *Howellictis valentini* from Chad by bigger dental size with more
36 crowded lower premolars, and p3 with distal accessory cuspid; and from the late
37 Miocene *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* from Kenya, by shorter p4 and
38 buccolingually shorter m1 protoconid. It also differs from *H. valentini* and *Er.*
39 *lothagamensis* in absence or residual presence of the m2 alveolus. We infer *M.*
40 *benfieldi* was an opportunistic, medium-sized carnivoran with semifossorial
41 abilities, comparable to its living relative *Mellivora capensis*. A cladistics analysis
42 was performed and our phylogenetic hypothesis places *M. benfieldi* as the sister
43 group of *M. capensis*. Mellivorini contains *M. benfieldi*, *M. capensis* and *H.*
44 *valentini*. Additionally, we also include *Er. lothagamensis* and the Indian
45 *Promellivora punjabiensis*. We propose the creation of one new tribe within
46 Mellivorinae: Eomellivorini (*Eomellivora* spp. + *Ekorus*). It shares a common
47 ancestor with Mellivorini and is characterized by large size, a robust and sharp
48 dentition, as well as a skeleton with cursorial adaptations.

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INTRODUCTION

51

52 Mellivorinae Gray, 1865, is the subfamily of Mustelidae that contains
53 *Mellivora capensis* (honey badger or ratel) as its single living member. *Mellivora*
54 *capensis* is the largest African terrestrial mustelid, and is widespread in Africa,
55 Southwest Asia, and the Indian subcontinent (Larivière and Jennings, 2009). The
56 African fossil record of this subfamily is diverse and shows a relatively long
57 evolutionary history (Werdelin and Peigné, 2010). It comprises the middle-late
58 Miocene '*Eomellivora tugenensis* Morales and Pickford, 2005a from the Ngorora
59 Fm., Kenya (ca. 12 Ma); the late Miocene *Howellictis valentini* Bonis, Peigné, Guy,
60 Likius, Makaye, Vignaud, and Brunet, 2009, from the locality Toros Menalla 192,
61 Chad (ca. 7 Ma); three distinct forms in Lothagam, Kenya (Werdelin, 2003),
62 including the very large *Ekorus ekakeran* Werdelin, 2003 from the Lower Nawata
63 Fm. (ca. 7 Ma), smaller *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* Werdelin, 2003, and an
64 indeterminate mellivorinae that may also be the same taxon (L. Werdelin, pers
65 comm.) from the Upper member of the Nawata Fm. (6.5-5.5 Ma). Finally, the fossil
66 record of *Mellivora* Storr, 1780, includes the Mio-Pliocene *Mellivora benfieldi*
67 Hendeby, 1978a from Langebaanweg, South Africa (early Pliocene, ca. 5.2 Ma), and
68 doubtfully at the Middle Awash Fm. of Ethiopia, (ca. 6-5.5 Ma) (Haile-Selassie and
69 Howell, 2009); and the late Pliocene/extant *Mellivora capensis* (Schreber, 1776).
70 Outside Africa this subfamily occurs in Brisighella, Italy (MN13, ca. 5.4 Ma)
71 (Rook et al., 1991), with the remains of *M. benfieldi*, and in Eurasia and North
72 America with the remains of the giant mustelid *Eomellivora* Zdansky, 1924.
73 Fragmentary remains have been described from India and Pakistan from the
74 Siwaliks Hills, comprising three forms: (1) *Sivamellivora necrophila* (Pilgrim,
75 1932) from the Lower Siwaliks, Chinji Fm ca. 14–11.2 Ma (Patnaik, 2013), (2)

76 *Promellivora punjabensis* (Lydekker, 1884), from the late Miocene sediments of
77 the Dhok Pathan Fm, 10.2–5.3 Ma (Patnaik, 2013), and (3) *Mellivora sivalensis*
78 (Falconer, 1868) from the upper part of the Siwaliks in the Pinjor Fm, Pleistocene
79 (2.58–1.7 Ma) (Patnaik, 2013), which is morphologically similar to *M. capensis*
80 (Falconer 1868; Lydekker, 1884; Pilgrim, 1932; Petter, 1987; Bonis et al., 2009).

81 Langebaanweg (LBW), ‘E’ Quarry, is a late Miocene – early Pliocene fossil
82 site (Fig. 1) that has yielded one of the richest and best-preserved Neogene
83 mammal assemblages in Africa (Hendey, 1981a; 1989). It is located within the
84 West Coast Fossil Park near Vredenburg, Western Province, South Africa. Fossils
85 were first discovered at ‘E’ Quarry in 1965 when phosphate mining started at the
86 Varswater mine (Hendey, 1989). Langebaanweg has been interpreted as an estuary
87 that formed during a transgressive phase with associated marine flooding of the
88 coastal areas (Hendey, 1989; Roberts et al., 2011; Cohen et al., 2018). Repeated
89 fluctuations in sea levels influenced the geology of Langebaanweg; and the
90 depositional environments preserved there include shallow marine, estuarine, marsh
91 and fluvial systems (Hendey, 1989; Roberts et al., 2011).

92 The fossils occur in the Varswater Fm., which is divided into four members
93 that have different ages, spatial relationships, thickness, lithology, and depositional
94 settings (Roberts et al., 2011): (1) Langeenheid Clayey Sand (LCSM), (2) Konings
95 Vlei Gravel (KGM), (3) Langeberg Quartz Sand (LQSM) and (4) Muishond
96 Fontein Pelletal Phosphorite Members (MPPM). The main fossil bearing deposits
97 of the formation are the MPPM and LQSM. All the terrestrial carnivoran material
98 from ‘E’ Quarry was found in these two members (Hendey, 1974, 1976, 1978a,
99 1978b, 1980, 1989). There are two different highly fossiliferous beds in the MPPM:
100 Beds 3aN and Bed 3aS. These are interpreted as river channel deposits (Hendey,

101 1989), and are inferred as very close in age, with Bed 3aS slightly older (Hendey,
102 1981b). The ages of LQSM and MPPM were estimated by palaeomagnetic data and
103 global sea level reconstructions as $\sim 5.15 \pm 0.1$ Ma, suggesting that the fossils
104 accumulated at an early stage in the Early Pliocene transgression (Roberts et al.,
105 2011). Baard's Quarry (Hendey, 1974, 1978c) is another fossil deposit in LBW that
106 includes carnivoran fossils, but it is interpreted as much recent deposit (late
107 Pliocene or early Pleistocene) (Hendey, 1978c).

108 Since Hendey completed a series of monographic studies on the LBW
109 carnivorans (Hendey, 1972, 1974, 1976, 1978a, 1978b, 1980, 1981a, 1989), the
110 LBW's fauna has been extensively cited and has become a reference fauna for Mio-
111 Pliocene studies of carnivorans. Recent studies of the LBW carnivorans have
112 focused on hyaenids (Werdelin et al., 1994), the saber toothed cats
113 *Amphimachairodus* sp. and *Dinofelis* sp. (Werdelin and Lewis, 2001; Werdelin and
114 Sardella, 2007), phocids (Govender et al., 2011, 2012; Govender, 2015), and
115 recently the giant mustelids *Sivaonyx hendeyi* (Morales, Pickford and Soria, 2005)
116 and *Plesiogulo* aff. *monspessulanus* (see Valenciano and Govender, 2020).
117 Additionally, some ecological and biomechanical studies have been performed
118 (Werdelin, 2006; Stynder, 2009; Tseng and Stynder, 2011; Oldfield et al., 2012;
119 Stynder et al. 2012, 2018; Stynder and Kupczik, 2013; Hartstone-Rose and Stynder
120 2013; Hartstone-Rose et al., 2016).

121 The current study presents a review of the published and previously
122 unpublished material referred to the mellivorine *Mellivora benfieldi* Hendey, 1978a
123 from LBW, the type locality of this species. The goal of this study is to update our
124 knowledge of this significant mustelid. It will be compared to other mellivorines

125 from Eurasian and African Mio/Pliocene localities to better understand the
126 taxonomy, paleobiology and ecology of this group of mustelids.

127

128 MATERIAL AND METHODS

129

130 **Nomenclature and Measurements**

131 Dental nomenclature follows Ginsburg (1999) and Smith and Dodson (2003).
132 Anatomical descriptions are based primarily on Barone (1999, 2000), Waibl et al.
133 (2005), Evans and de Lahunta (2010, 2013) and Ercoli et al. (2013, 2015), and the
134 terminology conforms to the standard of the Nomina anatomica Veterinaria (NAV;
135 Waibl et al., 2005). Measurements were taken using Mitutoyo Absolute digital
136 calipers to the nearest 0.1 mm (Fig. 2; Tables 1-2; Table S1-2).

137

138 **Abbreviations**

139 **Institutional Abbreviations**—**AMNH**, American Museum of Natural History,
140 New York, USA; **BAT-3**, Batallones-3 locality collection from MNCN; **BSPG**,
141 Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontologie und Geologie, Munich, Germany;
142 **F:AM**, collection housed in the Frick Collection of the Division of Paleontology,
143 AMNH, New York, USA; **FCPT**, Fundación Conjunto Paleontológico de Teruel-
144 Dinópolis, Museo Aragonés de Paleontología, Teruel, Spain; **FMNH**, Field
145 Museum of Natural History Chicago, Illinois, USA; **FSL**, Université Claude
146 Bernard Lyon 1 Lyon, France; **ICP**, Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel
147 Crusafont, Barcelona, Spain; **IPUW**, Institut für Paläontologie, Universität Wien,
148 Vienna, Austria; **ISAM**, Iziko South African Museum, Cape Town, South Africa;
149 **KNM**, Nairobi National Museum, National Museums of Kenya, Nairobi, Kenya;

150 **MGUV**, Museu de Geologia de la Universitat de València, Burjassot, Spain;
151 **MNCN**, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales Madrid, Spain; **MNHN**, Muséum
152 national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France; **NHMW**, Naturhistorisches Museum
153 Wien, Vienna, Austria; **NRM**, Naturhistoriska riksmuseet, Stockholm, Sweden;
154 **PIN**, Palaeontological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia;
155 **PMU**, Palaeontological Museum, University of Uppsala, Uppsala, Sweden; **SAM-**
156 **PQL**, Quaternary Palaeontology (Langebaanweg), Iziko South African Museum,
157 Cape Town, South Africa; **SAM-ZM**, Zoology Mammals, Iziko South African
158 Museum, Cape Town, South Africa; **SMNS**, Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde,
159 Stuttgart, Germany; **USNM**, Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History
160 (The Smithsonian Museum Support Center, Division of Mammals MSC, Suitland,
161 USA).

162

163 **Study Material**

164 We have re-analyzed the *Mellivora benfieldi* material described by Hendey (1974,
165 1978a) as well as new material housed in the Cenozoic collections at the Iziko
166 South African Museum (ISAM). The comparative material includes original
167 material of: *Zodiolestes daimonelixensis* Rigg, 1942 from the early-late Arikarean
168 (c. 23 Ma) Harrison Formation, Sioux County, Nebraska (USA), housed at FMNH
169 comprising a complete skeleton; dentition of *Iberictis buloti* Ginsburg and Morales,
170 1992 from els Casots (16.5–16.3 Ma, MN4, Vallès-Penedès Basin, Barcelona,
171 Spain) housed at ICP (Valenciano et al., 2020); *Sthenictis* sp. (F:AM 25235 and
172 25236) from Burge Fauna, early Clarendonian (Valentine Formation, Nebraska,
173 USA, 13-12 Ma, c. MN7/8) comprising a complete skeleton; *Laphictis mustelinus*
174 Viret, 1933 from the localities of Can Mata 1 (MN7/8, els Hostalets

175 de Pierola, Barcelona, Spain) comprising a skull and dentition housed at ICP
176 (Villalta Comella and Crusafont Pairó 1943; Crusafont and Truyols 1954; Petter
177 1963), and by original photographs from La Grive-Saint-Alban (MN7/8, France)
178 housed at FSL, Erkertshofen 2 (MN4, Germany) (Viret 1933; Roth 1989), housed
179 at BSPG, and Steinheim (MN7, Germany), housed at SMNS (including some
180 postcranial remains, see Helbing 1936); *Eomellivora piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965 from
181 Batallones-3, Spain (late Miocene, MN10, ca. 9 Ma), which is stored in the
182 collections of the Department of Paleobiología at the MNCN and comprises cranial
183 (Valenciano et al., 2015) and unpublished postcranial remains; *Eomellivora wimani*
184 Zdansky, 1924 from Shangyingou and Liuwangou from China, MN12-13, housed
185 at PMU, comprised of dentognathic material; *Plesiogulo monspessulanus* Viret,
186 1939, from Montpellier (MN14, France) housed at FSL, the dentognathic Spanish
187 material from Venta del Moro (Montoya et al., 2011) and Las Casiones (Alcalá et
188 al., 1994), housed at MGUV and FCPT respectively, as well as the cranial and
189 postcranial fossils of *P. aff. monspessulanus* from Langebaanweg (Hendey, 1978a;
190 Valenciano and Govender, 2020); and *Mellivora capensis* from the South African
191 Pleistocene sites of Elandsfontein, 1-0.6 Ma (Klein et al., 2007), Swartklip 1 (0.1
192 Ma), and the Holocene sites of Tygerfontein and Sea Harvest (e.g., Hendey, 1974,
193 1978a) housed at ISAM. *Ekorus ekakeran* from Lower Nawata Fm., Lothagam,
194 Kenya (late Miocene, c. a., 7 Ma) (Werdelin, 2003) from the research collection of
195 L. Werdelin (cast) housed at NRM. The Pleistocene *Gulo schlosseri* Kormos, 1914,
196 was also studied based on a cast of the holotype from Püspökfürdo, Hungary,
197 housed at NHMW and the publications by Kormos (1914) and Bonifay (1971). We
198 further examined photographs of the holotypes of *Dehmictis vorax* (Dehm, 1950)
199 from Wintershof-West (MN3, Germany), housed at BSPG, *Ischyriectis zibethoides*

200 (Blainville, 1842) from Sansan (MN6, France) housed at MNHN, *Eomellivora*
201 *ursogulo* (Orlov, 1948) from Grebeniki, Ukraine, MN11 housed at PIN (also
202 available as a cast at IPUW and NHMW), and *Erokomellivora lothagamensis*,
203 known from the Upper member of the Nawata Fm. Lothagam, Kenya (6.5–5.5 Ma)
204 (Werdelin, 2003). Analyses of the Miocene ‘*Eomellivora*’ *tugenensis*, from the
205 Ngorora formation (Kenya), ca. 12 Ma (Morales and Pickford, 2005a) and the late
206 Miocene *Howellicteis valentini* from the locality Toros Menalla 192 (Chad), ca. 7
207 Ma (de Bonis et al., 2009) are based on published descriptions.

208 The extant specimens used for comparison are: *Martes foina* (Erxleben, 1777)
209 (MNCN-3684, 3685, 21673, 3705), *Mellivora capensis* (AMNH-51952, 81232,
210 81848, 83450, 169085, 169088, 69499, 81831, 34263, 34264, 119622, 119949;
211 USNM-270224; NRM-A582462, A583405, A591017, A605023, A580357,
212 A591015, A584514; SAM-ZM-41483, 41666); *Pekania pennanti* (Erxleben, 1777)
213 (FMNH-141987, 141989, 129326, 134449, 134450, 203682, 160116, 153811,
214 165360, 165358, 6343, 165359, 10881, 89456, 72959, 129325, 81486, 6341, 6342;
215 AMNH-121554, 121556); *Gulo gulo* Linnaeus (1758) (MNCN-16748; USNM
216 275160, 272316, A06231, 265649, 242705, 108654, 096147; NRMA825005,
217 A845012, 20055154, 20115498, A815010, A587719, A885007, A795005,
218 A825004; FMNH-151027, 129317).

219

220 **Cladistic Analysis**

221 In order to analyze the phylogenetic position of *Mellivora benfieldi* relative to
222 better-known mellivorines, gulonines and primitive Miocene mustelids from
223 Africa, Eurasia and North America, we performed a cladistics analysis of 18
224 operational taxonomic units (OTU), and 100 cranial, dental and postcranial

225 characters. All characters were equally weighted and unordered. The complete list
226 of taxa, characters and the character-taxon matrix are available in Supplemental
227 File 1–2. We restricted our analysis to the early Miocene oligobunine *Zodiolestes*
228 *daimonelixensis* (outgroup), *Dehmictis vorax* and *Iberictis buloti*, the middle
229 Miocene medium-size *Ischyriictis zibethoides*, *Laphictis mustelinus* and *Sthenictis*
230 sp., the late Miocene *Ekorus ekakeran*, *Eomellivora piveteaui*, *Eomellivora wimani*,
231 *Eomellivora ursogulo*, *Howellictis valentini*, and *Plesiogulo monspessulanus*
232 (including *P. aff. monspessulanus* from Langebaanweg), and the Pleistocene *Gulo*
233 *schlosseri*. Additionally, the living mustelids *Mellivora capensis*, *Martes foina*,
234 *Pekania pennanti* and *Gulo gulo* were analysed. We excluded the poorly known
235 African ‘*Eomellivora*’ *tugenensis* and *Erokomellivora lothagamensis*. The cladistic
236 analysis was performed set using in PAUP*4.0b10 (Swofford, 2002). This analysis
237 yielded 6 parsimonious trees with 247 steps by the branch-and-bound-search, with
238 a consistency index (CI) of 0.4494, a homoplasy index (HI) of 0.5506 and a
239 retention index (RI) of 0.6486. Clade support was calculated using bootstrap
240 analysis with 1000 replicates, and a Bremer support values. Moreover, we obtained
241 a Bootstrap 50% majority-rule consensus tree with 249 steps, a CI of 0.4458, HI of
242 0.5542 and a RI of 0.6434.

243

244 SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

245

246 Order CARNIVORA Bowdich, 1821

247 Suborder CANIFORMIA Kretzoi, 1943

248 Family MUSTELIDAE Fischer, 1817

249 Subfamily MELLIVORINAE Gray, 1865

250 Genus *MELLIVORA* Storr, 1780

251 *MELLIVORA BENFIELDI* Hendey, 1978a

252

253 *Mellivora* aff. *punjabiensis* Hendey 1974 fig.6, (original description).

254

255 **Holotype**—SAM-PQL-42838, a left hemimandible with c, p2-4 and m1

256 figured by Hendey (1978a: fig.7).

257 **Type Locality**—Langebaanweg, MPPM.

258 **Other Localities**—Brisighella, MN13, Late Miocene, ca. 5.4 Ma (Italy),

259 Rook et al. (1991); Middle-Awash, Ethiopia (Haile-Selassie and Howell, 2009), ca.

260 6-5.5 Ma (Haile-Selassie et al. 2004).

261 **Referred Material from the Type Locality**—In Hendey, (1978a): SAM-

262 PQL-6385, left hemimandible with p4-m1; SAM-PQL-31273, right hemimandible

263 with m1; SAM-PQL-50443, right hemimandible with p4-m1; SAM-PQL-50541,

264 right M1; tentatively SAM-PQL-40080, left ulna, and SAM-PQL-45384, right

265 radius. New Material: SAM-PQL-72167, right I3; SAM-PQL-69620C, left C;

266 SAM-PQL-51386, left C; SAM-PQL-50107, right P3; SAM-PQL-72165, left P3;

267 SAM-PQL-72168, right P3 fragment; SAM-PQL-72227, right P4 fragment with

268 missing protocone; SAM-PQL-72174, left hemimandible with p2-m1, and m2

269 alveolus; SAM-PQL-69620B, left fragmentary hemimandible with m1 and m2

270 alveolus; SAM-PQL-50002, left fragmentary hemimandible with m1; SAM-PQL-

271 50105, left fragmentary hemimandible with broken p4-m1 at the base of the crown;

272 SAM-PQL-50106, right fragmentary mandibular body with c, p2-p4 alveoli; SAM-

273 PQL-50444, left p2; SAM-PQL-72176, left humerus fragment including the distal

274 diaphysis and distal epiphysis; SAM-PQL-41875, right humerus fragment,

275 including the distal part of the diaphysis; SAM-PQL-72175, complete right ulna;
276 SAM-PQL-25606, right ulna fragment comprising the proximal epiphysis and two
277 thirds of the diaphysis; SAM-PQL-69620A, right ulna fragment comprising the
278 proximal epiphysis and one thirds of the diaphysis; SAM-PQL-69620E, right
279 metacarpal V; SAM-PQL-42486, right proximal femur epiphysis; SAM-PQL-
280 41513A, left distal femur epiphysis; SAM-PQL-69634B, right calcaneum.

281 **Emended Diagnosis**—Modified after Hendey (1978a). Smaller than the
282 living *Mellivora capensis*. P3 slender, double-rooted and without accessory cusps;
283 M1 with long parastyle, mesially oriented protocone, and a lingual platform
284 relatively expanded, but without a prominent cingulum around the protocone; sharp
285 lower premolars; p1 absent; p3 with distal accessory cuspid; slender p4 with mesial
286 and distal accessory cusps; m1 without metaconid, and with a narrow, sharp
287 talonid that has a central, low hypoconid, and no hypoconulid; m2 absent or
288 vestigial. Humerus with enlarged deltopectoral crest that exceeds the distal half of
289 the diaphysis, enlarged supraepicondylar crest laterally projected, and the medial
290 epicondyle, proximodistally and medially projected; Ulna with enlarged olecranon
291 process medially projected; calcaneus with a short calcaneal tuber and the M.
292 quadratus plantae process laterally expanded.

293 **Differential Diagnosis**—Differs from '*Eomellivora tugenensis*' in smaller
294 size, and M1 protocone more mesially placed. Differs from *Howellictis valentini* in
295 larger teeth with more crowded premolars, mandibular condyle not elevated above
296 the cheek teeth, p2 less buccolingually rotated, p3 with distal accessory cuspid,
297 absent or residual m2, and deltoid crest of the humerus extends beyond the middle
298 of the diaphysis. Differs from *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* in shorter p4,
299 buccolingually shorter m1 protoconid, and absent or residual m2 alveolus. Differs

300 from *Ekorus ekakeran* and *Eomellivora piveteaui* in much smaller size, absence of
301 m2 and p1; in humerus with enlarged pectoral crest and medial epicondyle, distal
302 epiphysis craniocaudally compressed; ulna with the tuber olecrani medially
303 projected, and unreduced articular circumference; calcaneus more robust and
304 shorter with sustentacular facet medially projected and groove for the M. quadratus
305 plantae more developed. Differs from *Mellivora capensis* in slenderer P3, p4; M1
306 with longer parastyle, mesial protocone; absence of the distal accessory cusp on P3
307 and the mesial accessory cusp on p3; m1 talonid narrower, sharper and more
308 reduced with a central hypoconid, and without a lingual basined depression;
309 calcaneus with smaller sustentacular facet.

310

311 **Description**

312 **SAM-PQL-72167**—A caniniform, right I3 (Fig. 3A1-3; Table 1), with a
313 single cusp that curves distally. There is a sharp crista as well as a distinct cingulum
314 in the lingual face.

315 **SAM-PQL-69620**—Left C (Fig. 3B1-3; Table 1). It is oval in cross-section
316 and worn, especially the tip, buccal and lingual sides. The root swells mesiodistally,
317 and the root is encircled by concentric rings.

318 **SAM-PQL-51386**—Left C (Fig. 3C1-3; Table 1). Its cusp is curved distally.
319 Like SAM-PQL-72167 (Fig. 3A1-3), it has a sharp crista from the tip to the lingual
320 side, as well as a distinct lingual cingulum.

321 **SAM-PQL-50107**—Right P3 (Fig. 3D1-3; Table 1). It is double rooted,
322 elongate and unicuspid, with a lingual bulge. Its cusp is mesially located and shows
323 wear. It has a well-developed cingulum.

324 **SAM-PQL-72165**—Left P3 (Fig. 3E1–2; Table 1). It belongs to a very
325 young adult individual. No preserved roots or wear facets. Very similar to SAM-
326 PQL-50107. It has a mesial and distal crista. Its distal cingulum is crowned.

327 **SAM-PQL-72227**—Right P4 (Fig. 3F1–3; Table 1). It is broken with a
328 missing paracone. It is buccolingually robust. There is no parastyle. There is an
329 inflection between the protocone and parastyle. The mesial side is worn. The
330 protocone is missing, however, the remains suggest that it is in line with the
331 parastyle, and is not mesiodistally reduced. There is no carnassial notch and the
332 occlusal area is quite worn. There is a concavity in the buccal wall between the
333 paracone and metastyle. A thick cingulum surrounds the entire crown.

334 **SAM-PQL-72174**—Left hemimandible with worn p2-m1, and an m2
335 alveolus (Fig. 3G1–4; Table 2). The mandibular corpus is tall and lateromedially
336 broad. There are longitudinal cracks on the corpus (Fig. 3G1–2), as it was exposed
337 prior to burial. The rostral part of the mandibular symphysis is missing as are the
338 coronoid, articular and angular processes. The most caudal part of the mandibular
339 symphysis reaches the distal position of p3. There are two mandibular foramina,
340 one below p2 and the other below the junction of p3-4. Ventrally, there is a wide
341 muscular attachment for the M. digastricus. The masseteric fossa is deep and in its
342 ventral area has a large muscular attachment for M. masseter pars superficialis and
343 M. masseter pars profunda. There is an alveolus for the C. There is no p1 alveolus.
344 The p2 is buccolingually angled and unicuspid. Both p2 and p3 are double rooted,
345 and distally wide. The main cuspid of the p3 is mesially located. There is a sharp
346 cristid from the tip of this cuspid to the mesial part of the tooth. There is a small
347 wear facet on the distal accessory cuspid, and the cuspid is smaller to those of the
348 holotype SAM-PQL-42838. The p4 is elongated, subrectangular and distally broad.

349 It has a small mesial accessory cuspid. Its main cuspid is taller than the m1
350 paraconid. Its mesial cristid has a sharp edge. There is a worn distal accessory
351 cuspid. A large cingulid surrounds the mesial and distal areas of p4. The occlusal
352 surface of the m1 is worn. It is an elongate molar with a maximum width at base of
353 the protoconid. The trigonid occupies more than three-fourths of the total length of
354 the tooth. The protoconid is taller than the paraconid, and there is no metaconid.
355 The talonid is low and buccolingually compressed. The only talonid cuspid is the
356 hypoconid. There is a small, circular alveolus for the m2 (Fig. 3G3).

357 **SAM-PQL-69620B**—Left fragmentary hemimandible with m1 and m2
358 alveolus (Fig. 3I1–3; Table 2). The preserved mandibular corpus is very broad. It
359 has longitudinal cracks on the corpus. The masseteric fossa is deeper than that of
360 SAM-PQL-72174 and SAM-PQL-42836. The mandibular bone surrounding the m1
361 is very porous, indicating pathology. The m1 is larger than SAM-PQL-72174 and
362 SAM-PQL-42836. There is a large wear facet on the distolingual part of the talonid.
363 A low and centrally placed hypoconid is present. It has a large cingulid encircling
364 the tooth. There is a small, circular alveolus for the m2.

365 **SAM-PQL-50002**—Left fragmentary hemimandible with m1 (Fig. 3J1–3;
366 Table 2). The mandibular corpus is slender. The enamel of the m1 is partially
367 dissolved and is missing on the mesial and distolingual area. The protoconid is
368 taller than the paraconid. There are neither a metaconid nor an entoconid. The
369 talonid has a low and centrally located hypoconulid. A distinct cingulid is present at
370 the base of the entire tooth. There is no m2 alveolus.

371 **SAM-PQL-50105**—Large fragment of left hemimandible with p4-m1 broken
372 at the base of the crown (Fig. 3K1–2; Table 2). The measurements of the teeth are

373 the smallest of the entire sample from LBW (Table 2), but the absence of the
374 crowns may underestimate the sizes of the actual teeth. There is no m2 alveolus.

375 **SAM-PQL-50106**—Right rostral mandibular corpus fragment with the
376 alveolus for c, the distal root of p2, each of p3 and the mesial one of p4 (Fig. 3L1–
377 2; Table 2).

378 **SAM-PQL-50444**—Left p2 (Fig. 3H1–3; Table 2), similar in the overall
379 morphology to SAM-PQL-72174. It has long roots. The cuspid is tall and mesially
380 situated. The distal cingulid is prominent.

381 **SAM-PQL-72176**—A partial humerus comprised of two thirds of the shaft,
382 and the distal epiphysis (Fig. 4A–F; Table S1). Longitudinal cracks extend along
383 the main axis of the bone and the surface is covered by root etching. The cortical
384 bone of the diaphysis is thick (Fig. 4F). On the cranial surface, the pectoral and
385 deltoid crests are present and are joined at the midpoint of the diaphysis (Fig. 4A).
386 The pectoral crest projects medially. The distal epiphysis is very broad. The lateral
387 epicondylar crest, onto which the M. anconeus and M. extensor carpi radialis
388 attach, is expanded. The distal epiphysis is rectangular and craniocaudally
389 compressed. The olecranon fossa is low, broad and proximodistally flattened. The
390 caudal part of the capitulum is deep and lateromedially short. There is no a
391 supratrochlear foramen. On the cranial side, the trochlea and the capitulum are
392 proximodistally short and mediolaterally elongated. The medial epicondyle is
393 dorsoventrally and medially enlarged, increasing the surface area for the attachment
394 of M. pronator teres and M. flexor digitorum profundus. A large supracondylar
395 (entepicondylar) foramen is present.

396 **SAM-PQL-41875**—Right humerus fragment, containing partial distal
397 diaphysis (Fig. 4G–K; Table S1). The thick cortical bone and the large lateral

398 epicondylar crest are very similar to SAM-PQL-72176. It also has longitudinal
399 cracks along the main axis of the humerus. There are several pits and perpendicular
400 bite marks, suggesting it was gnawed on.

401 **SAM-PQL-72175**—Complete right ulna (Fig. 4L–O; Table S1). It is robust,
402 and sigmoid in cranial view. The olecranon is similar to SAM-PQL-40080, which
403 is large and medially projected, without any tubercle on the cranial aspect of the
404 olecranon. Thus, the attachment of the long head of the *M. triceps brachii* is also
405 medially projected, more than that of SAM-PQL-40080. The trochlea is
406 proximodistally short and craniocaudally deep. The anconeal process curves
407 distally. The diaphysis is mediolaterally compressed but craniocaudally long. The
408 proximal half of the diaphysis projects laterally, and the distal half projects
409 medially. There is a prominent crest for the attachment of the *M. pronator*
410 *quadratus*. The distal epiphysis is robust, with the articular circumference
411 projecting cranially. The styloid process is large and round.

412 **SAM-PQL-25606**—Right ulna fragment (Fig. 4P; Table S1), comprised of
413 the proximal epiphysis and two-thirds of the diaphysis. It is slightly smaller than
414 SAM-PQL-40080 and SAM-PQL-72175, but larger than SAM-PQL-69620A.

415 **SAM-PQL-69620A**—Right ulna fragment (Fig. 4Q; Table S1), comprised
416 of proximal epiphysis and one-third of the diaphysis. The olecranon is partially
417 gnawed off. It may represent a young adult, because of its small size and porous
418 nature.

419 **SAM-PQL-69620E**—Right fifth metacarpal (Mc V). A short and robust
420 bone (Fig. 4R–W; Table S1). The dorsal surface of the metacarpal is rectilinear, but
421 the palmar surface is slightly concave, because of the palmar projection of the
422 proximal epiphysis. This epiphysis is subquadrangular, with the lateromedial axis

423 longer than the dorsopalmar axis. There is a small hole in the middle of the
424 proximal epiphysis. The lateral facet for the Mc IV is large and L-shaped. There is
425 a relatively large and round groove for the attachment of the M. extensor carpi
426 ulnaris on the lateral face of the metacarpal. The diaphysis is slightly
427 dorsopalmarily flattened. The distal epiphysis is asymmetric, with the lateral
428 margin larger than the medial.

429 **SAM-PQL-42486**— Right proximal femur epiphysis (Fig. 5A-E; Table S2).
430 It is eroded and broken. There is bone regrowth and bone expose all over the
431 surface. The head and greater trochanter are damage. The head is large and
432 medially projected. The neck is short. The greater trochanter is relatively large and
433 the trochanteric fossa is deep. In lateral view, the greater trochanter is
434 craniocaudally wide, and has a rugose muscular attachment for the M. gluteus
435 medius (Fig. 5D). The lesser trochanter is well developed and extends
436 lateromedially. The rest of the diaphysis is missing.

437 **SAM-PQL-41513A**—Left distal femur epiphysis (Fig. 5F-I; Table S2),
438 probably belonging to the same individual as SAM-PQL-42486. Part of the cortical
439 bone is missing, like the area around the medial condyle. This epiphysis is
440 subrectangular in distal view. The lateral condyle is lateromedially wider than the
441 medial one. The trochlea is shallow. There are large scars for the attachment of the
442 M. gastrocnemius on the caudolateral and caudomedial sides of the condyles.

443 **SAM-PQL-69634B**— Right calcaneum (Fig. 5J-O; Table S2). The entire
444 bone shows secondary growth. It is nearly complete, with the exception of the most
445 distodorsal part of the astragalar platform. The calcaneal tuberosity is robust, and
446 lateromedially wide, with no process. The gastrocnemial groove on the proximal
447 part of the tuberosity is shallow. There are lateral and medial bulges on the

448 calcaneal tuberosity for the tendon of the M. superficial digital flexor. The body of
449 the calcaneus is dorsoplantarily enlarged. The sustentaculum tali extends medially.
450 In plantar view, there is a large falciform scar for the ligament of the M. long
451 plantar, located lateral to the groove for the tendon of the M. flexor digitorum
452 lateralis. On the laterodistal portion of the bone, there is a laterally extended
453 quadratus plantae process. Additionally, there is a crest from that process to the
454 ectal facet, to which the M. quadratus plantae is attached.

455

456

DISCUSSION

457

***Mellivora benfieldi* and Mio/Pliocene African and Indian Mellivorines**

459 The mellivorine from LBW was first reported by Hendeby (1974), who
460 described a fragmentary mandible (SAM-PQL-6385) as *Mellivora* aff.
461 *punjabiensis*. The material was collected from ‘E’ Quarry, MPPM, bed 3aS of the
462 Varswater Fm. Later, he redefined this material and erected *M. benfieldi* from
463 MPPM (bed 3aS and bed 3aN) based on several mandibles (SAM-PQL-42838,
464 SAM-PQL-31273, SAM-PQL-50443, SAM-PQL-6385), an M1 (SAM-PQL-
465 50541), and, tentatively on a complete ulna and radius (SAM-PQL-40080, SAM-
466 PQL-45384) (Hendeby, 1978a).

467 Most of the new specimens of *M. benfieldi* described in the present study are
468 from the MPPM (bed 3aS and N), and for the first time this taxon is reported from
469 the LQSM (Table S3). The minimum number of individuals known from MPPM
470 and LQSM, based on the m1, is eight. This sample of *M. benfieldi* from LBW
471 displays wide biometric and morphological variability in dentition and in the
472 postcranial bones (Figs. 3–6; Tables 1–2, Table S1-2). This variability includes: a

473 better developed distal accessory cuspid on p3 of SAM-PQL-42838 (holotype) in
474 relation with SAM-PQL-72174; and a better developed mesial accessory cuspid on
475 p4 of SAM-PQL-50443 and SAM-PQL-42836 compared to the other specimens.
476 However, the most noteworthy variation is on the lower molars. The specimens
477 with preserved lower molars come from Beds 3aN and Bed 3aS of MPPM (Table
478 S3). The m1 of SAM-PQL-72174 and SAM-PQL-6385 have a relatively wide
479 protoconid and talonid compared to SAM-PQL-42836 and the extremely slender
480 SAM-PQL-50002, which has damaged or dissolved enamel. SAM-PQL-72174 and
481 SAM-PQL-69620b have the first documented m2 alveolus in *M. benfieldi*. The
482 retention of the m2 alveolus in two specimens from the relatively older Bed 3aS,
483 represents 25% of the entire sample of *M. benfieldi*. This also means 50% of the
484 mandibles from Bed 3aS had m2s (Table S3). This study suggests that this trait is
485 variable, although the low occurrence in the LBW population points toward the m2
486 disappearing in this mustelid through the time. Some intraspecific variation in *M.*
487 *benfieldi* may be explained by sexual dimorphism, with large specimens interpreted
488 as males and smaller ones as females, as is the case in *M. capensis* (Begg et al.,
489 2003; Larivière and Jennings, 2009). This extensive variability should be taken into
490 account when interpreting other African mellivorines from the fossil record. For
491 instance, the occurrence of m2 in the late Miocene *Howellictis* Bonis, Peigné, Guy,
492 Likus, Makaye, Vignaud, and Brunet, 2009 and *Erokomellivora* Werdelin, 2003 is
493 interpreted as a primitive trait for the group, and has been used to separate it from
494 *Mellivora*, where it disappeared (Werdelin, 2003; Werdelin and Peigné, 2010).
495 Additional traits are needed to distinguish between these genera.

496 *Mellivora benfieldi* has also been described from: Brisighella, Italy (late
497 Miocene, MN13, ca. 5.4 Ma) represented by a mandible fragment with p3-m1

498 (Rook et al., 1991) and Middle Awash Fm. of Ethiopia (ca. 6-5.5 Ma), represented
499 by a hemimandible with worn dentition, a broken m1 and a lower canine (Haile-
500 Selassie and Howell, 2009), though this referral is dubious. The mellivorine from
501 Brisighella can undoubtedly be attributed to *M. benfieldi*, as its morphological traits
502 conform to the known variability of this taxon. However, the Middle Awash
503 specimen AMW-VP-1/40 is different. Haile-Selassie and Howell (2009) suggested
504 that the Middle Awash species is likely to be ancestral to the South African *M.*
505 *benfieldi*. It has a relatively longer p4 (Table S4) and a m1 with a wider trigonid
506 and a more robust talonid to those from LBW. These traits are more comparable to
507 those of *Er. lothagamensis* from Lothagam (Werdelin, 2003), which lived at the
508 same time in Kenya. The absence of an m2 alveolus in AMW-VP-1/40 could be
509 explained as intraspecific variability in *Erokomellivora*, as it occurs in *M. benfieldi*
510 from LBW. *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* and AMW-VP-1/40 are worn and
511 incomplete specimens, we therefore consider the designation of AMW-VP-1/40 as
512 *M. aff. benfieldi* as valid until more material is available.

513 ‘*Eomellivora tugenensis*’ from the Ngorora formation in Kenya (Morales and
514 Pickford, 2005b) represents the oldest African mellivorine, ca. 12 Ma. It is a poorly
515 known mustelid of medium size, known from a fragmentary skull with a broken P4
516 and a complete M1, which could constitute an ancestral form of *Eomellivora*
517 (Valenciano et al., 2015, 2017a). *Mellivora benfieldi* shares some primitive traits
518 with ‘*E. tugenensis*’, such as a double rooted P3, and an M1 with an enlarged
519 parastyle, and a relatively well-developed metacone. However, *M. benfieldi* is
520 distinguished from ‘*E. tugenensis*’ by its smaller size, and a messially placed M1
521 protocone.

522 *Howellictis valentini* from the late Miocene locality of Toros Menalla 192
523 from Chad (ca. 7 Ma), is known from several specimens including skulls,
524 mandibles and some fragmentary postcranial remains (Bonis et al., 2009). It has
525 been interpreted as a basal mellivorine (Valenciano et al., 2017a), which is partially
526 in agreement with Bonis et al. (2009). *Mellivora benfieldi* also shares primitive
527 traits with *H. valentini* such as an elongated P3, a well- developed M1 parastyle,
528 and a slender p4. Additionally, both taxa have m1s with a low and reduced talonid.
529 *Mellivora benfieldi* differs from *H. valentini* by having a mandibular condyle that is
530 not elevated above the cheek teeth, larger teeth with more crowded premolars, p2
531 with less buccolingually rotation, p3 with a distal accessory cuspid, and absent or
532 residual m2. The fragmentary nature of the postcrania of *H. valentini* does not
533 allow a direct comparison to the postcrania of *M. benfieldi*, except for the humerus,
534 and the calcaneus. The deltoid crest of the humerus does not extend beyond the
535 middle of the diaphysis, and the calcanei of both small mellivorines are robust and
536 have similar proportions. *Howellictis valentini* is interpreted as a fully plantigrade
537 carnivore with a gait comparable to that of the ambulatory ones (Bonis et al., 2009),
538 but has not be reconstructed as fossorial. In contrast, we suggest *M. benfieldi* was
539 semifossorial.

540 *Promellivora punjabensis* was originally described as *Mellivora punjabiensis*
541 by Lydekker (1884), from the late Miocene sediments of the Dhok Pathan Fm., in
542 India (Pilgrim, 1932), based on an extremely fragmentary mandible with worn
543 dentition that has p2 and m1 alveoli and broken c, p3-p4. Pilgrim (1932) erected the
544 genus *Promellivora* based on this mandible, and described the presence of a p1
545 alveolus. Rook et al. (1991) distinguished *P. punjabensis* from *M. benfieldi* by its
546 much sturdier mandibular corpus, its relatively broader premolars and by the

547 presence of the p1. In our opinion, this material is very fragmentary, and a detailed
548 comparison cannot be made with *M. benfieldi*. More complete material of
549 *Promellivora* might clarify its relationship with other mellivorines.

550 The late Miocene Nawata Formation from Kenya has yielded two distinct
551 mellivorines, *Ekorus ekakeran* in the Lower Nawata Fm. ca. 7 Ma, and
552 *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* in the Upper member, ca. 6.5–5.5 Ma (Werdelin,
553 2003; Werdelin and Peigné, 2010), of which only *Er. lothagamensis* is a form close
554 to *Mellivora benfieldi*. *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* is only known from a
555 mandibular corpus with a broken p4 and a worn m1. It has the longest p4 in relation
556 to the m1 of the mellivorines analyzed for this study (Table S4). The size of the m1
557 of *Er. lothagamensis* overlaps with the larger specimens of *M. benfieldi* from LBW
558 (Fig. 6). Werdelin (2003) noted the similarities of *Er. lothagamensis* and *M.*
559 *benfieldi* from LBW but distinguished it as a new mellivorine that is more primitive
560 than *M. benfieldi*, because of its considerably longer p4, the more obliquely set and
561 shorter m1 trigonid, and, primarily because the retention of m2 (Fig. 7A-I). Only
562 SAM-PQL69620 of *M. benfieldi* (Figure 3I1-3) is close to *Er. lothagamensis* in
563 having a similar m1 morphology and retaining m2 alveolus. However, the less
564 obliquely set m1 trigonid, the shorter m1 talonid, and the reduced m2 alveolus in
565 SAM-PQL-69620 distinguishes these taxa.

566 The mellivorine from LBW can be ascribed to the genus *Mellivora* based on
567 several dental traits shared with *M. capensis* (Fig. 7; Table S5). These are a short
568 P4 with a buccal concavity between the paracone and the metastyle; a mandibular
569 condyle not elevated above the cheek teeth; presence of a distal accessory cuspid on
570 the p3; a mesial accessory cuspid on the p4; and the loss of m2. Furthermore,
571 several postcranial features, place the LBW taxon within *Mellivora*, such as a

572 humerus with craniocaudally compressed distal epiphysis, an ulna with medially
573 projected tuber olecrani and a medial projection of the M. pronator quadratus. The
574 oldest specimen of *M. capensis* in the fossil record comes from the middle Pliocene
575 of Laetoli (Tanzania, ca. 3.5 Ma) (Petter, 1987). It is fragmentary and poorly
576 preserved, which raises doubts about its specific assignation. Its presence is more
577 confident in the late Pliocene of Ahl al Oughlam (Morocco) ca. 2.5 Ma (Geraads,
578 1997). This taxon was abundant in Africa during the Pleistocene, especially in
579 South Africa (Hendey, 1974, 1978a; Werdelin and Peigné, 2010; Geraads, 2016). It
580 appears in the Cradle of Humankind World Heritage Site localities of Komdraai B,
581 2-1 Ma (Gommery et al., 2008), and Cooper's D, 1.4-1.5 Ma (De Ruiter et al.,
582 2009; O'Regan et al., 2013). It is better represented at Elandsfontein, 1-0.6 Ma
583 (Klein et al., 2007), Swartklip 1 (0.1 Ma), and the Holocene sites of Tygerfontein
584 and Sea Harvest (e.g., Hendey, 1974, 1978a). These middle-late
585 Pleistocene/Holocene remains of *M. capensis* are nearly identical to those of the
586 living populations, overlapping in the wide range of variability observed in the
587 dentition of *M. capensis* (Fig. 6; Table S5).

588 *Mellivora benfieldi* has a mosaic of primitive and derived traits. It is a more
589 primitive mellivorine than *M. capensis* by having less robust premolars (P3, p3-4),
590 double rooted P3; M1 with longer parastyle; M1 with a mesial protocone and with a
591 relatively smaller and weak lingual platform; smaller and fewer accessory cusps
592 (e.g., absence of the mesial and distal ones on the P3, and the mesial one in the p3),
593 m1 protoconid taller than the paraconid and a reduced sustentacular facet of the
594 calcaneus. The m1 is different, interpreted here as derived, being narrower, sharper
595 and with a more reduced talonid to that of *M. capensis*. It has a central hypoconid,
596 and has lost the hypoconulid and the lingual basin depression of the talonid, which

597 are present in *M. capensis*. The distinction between *M. benfieldi* and *M. capensis*
598 and their phylogenetic affinities have been questioned in the past (Petter, 1987;
599 Werdelin and Dehghani, 2011) as a result of the previously fragmentary material of
600 *M. benfieldi*, the similarities of the Pleistocene *M. capensis* with the living ones,
601 and because *M. capensis* is a highly plastic taxon in terms of dental variability
602 (A.V. pers. observ.). Henzey (1978a) indicated that *M. benfieldi* is suitable to be
603 ancestral to *M. capensis*, while Petter (1987) compared the classic material of *M.*
604 *benfieldi* (Henzey, 1974, 1978a) with the living *M. capensis*, and stated that neither
605 the measurements nor proportions of the teeth clearly separate the Langebaanweg
606 specimens from the extant *M. capensis*. Petter (1987) proposed that *M. benfieldi*
607 might represent the ancestral starting point of the *M. capensis* lineage, instead of
608 two separated taxa, with an increase in size in *M. capensis* through the Pliocene.
609 However, based on the updated sample of *M. benfieldi* and the discussed
610 morphological differences between both, we support their taxonomic
611 differentiation.

612 After comparing of the available postcrania of *M. benfieldi* and *M. capensis*, we
613 confirm that the ulna and radius (SAM-PQL-L40080 and SAM-PQL-45384)
614 figured by Henzey (1978a) belongs to *M. benfieldi*. The long bones of both
615 *Mellivora* species (*M. benfieldi* and *M. capensis*) are quite similar. The humerus has
616 a deltopectoral crest that exceeds the distal half of the diaphysis, a well-developed
617 pectoral crest that enlarges laterally, a supraepicondylar crest that projects laterally,
618 and a well-developed medial epicondyle, which is proximodistally expanded and
619 projected medially. These structures serve as areas of attachment for various
620 muscles that flex, pronate and supinate the forearm and flex and extend the wrist
621 (e.g., Gambaryan, 1974; Schutz and Guraznik, 2007; Samuels et al., 2013; Ercoli et

622 al., 2015, 2016; Fabre et al., 2015). These large epicondyles increase the muscle
623 mass located in the medial and distal segments of the forelimb and increase the
624 force produced when digging (Hildebrand 1985; Moore et al., 2013, Rose et al.,
625 2014) as observed in caviomorph rodents (Elissamburu and Vizcaíno, 2004;
626 Elissamburu and De Santis, 2011; Rose et al., 2014). *Mellivora benfieldi* has a
627 relatively narrow trochlea on the caudal part of the distal epiphysis of the humerus
628 compared to *M. capensis*. We calculated the index of fossorial ability (OLI sensu
629 Samuels et al., 2013 and IFA sensu Rose et al., 2014), and the index of ulnar
630 robustness (URI) of *M. benfieldi* ulnae and compared them with a broad sample of
631 living carnivorans. The index of fossorial ability, a recognized metric of
632 fossoriality, indicates the relative mechanical advantage for the elbow extensors
633 (*M. triceps brachii*, *M. anconeus*, and *M. epitrochlearis*) by an enlargement of the
634 olecranon process to apply a large force to the substrate during elbow joint
635 extension (Schutz and Guralnick, 2007; Moore et al., 2013; Samuels et al., 2013;
636 Rose et al., 2014). The values of OLI and IFA in SAM-PQL-72175 and SAM-PQL-
637 40080 are relatively high compared with the living carnivorans families but slight
638 lower than the badgers *Melogale moschata*, *Melogale personata*, and *M. capensis*,
639 being closer to the generalist mustelid *Galictis vittata* or the herpestid *Crossarchus*
640 *obscurus*, both with recognized digging abilities (e.g., Larivière and Jennings,
641 2009; Gilchrist et al., 2009). These high values indicate a relatively large olecranon
642 process in *M. benfieldi*, which suggests that it also had some digging abilities,
643 although not as progressive as living badgers (e.g., *Melogale* spp., *Meles* spp.,
644 *Taxidea taxus*, *M. capensis*). The URI indicates the degree of robustness of the ulna
645 and its ability to resist bending and shearing stresses and the relative area available
646 for the origin and insertion of forearm and manus flexors, pronators and supinators

647 (Hildebrand, 1985; Elissamburu and Vizcaíno, 2004; Elissamburu and De Santis,
648 2011; Samuels et al., 2013; Rose et al., 2014). *Mellivora benfieldi* is amongst the
649 highest values for the carnivoran sample of Samuels et al. (2013) and Rose et al.
650 (2014) indicating a very robust ulna. This index increases with fossorial ability in
651 scratch-digging rodents (Elissamburu and Vizcaíno, 2004; Lagaria and Youlatos,
652 2006), yet, we cannot rule out that the large curvature of the ulna overestimated this
653 index. The proximal epiphysis of the femur of *M. benfieldi* (SAM-PQL-42486; Fig.
654 5A-E) has a shorter neck than *M. capensis*, which could suggest lower degree of
655 mobility of the femur, with restriction to the parasagittal plane. This specimen,
656 however; has pathological regrown bone, which hides the real length of the femoral
657 neck. Finally, *M. benfieldi* has a robust Mc V (Fig. 4R-W) and robust calcaneus
658 (Fig. 5J-O) like *M. capensis*.

659 Based on the above observations, we conclude that *M. benfieldi* was a more
660 hypercarnivorous mustelid than *M. capensis*, with semifossorial abilities. We infer
661 *M. benfieldi* was an opportunistic carnivoran of medium size in the carnivore guild
662 of LBW. Two additional species of mustelid have been found at LBW, including
663 the giant gulonine *Plesiogulo* aff. *monspessulanus*, a species related to the living
664 wolverine (Valenciano et al., 2020a; Valenciano and Govender, 2020), and the
665 large, bunodont otter *Sivaonyx hendeyi* (Hendey, 1974, 1978a; Morales et al., 2005;
666 Morales and Pickford, 2005b; Valenciano and Govender, 2020). It is notable that
667 small musteloids are absent from LBW, when compared with other Mio/Pliocene
668 Eurasian localities, in which small martens, weasels, and skunks are present (e.g.,
669 Ginsburg, 1999; Montoya et al., 2011; Morales et al., 2015; Valenciano et al.,
670 2020b). The only Mio-Pliocene small mustelid described in Africa is
671 *Prepoecilogale* Petter and Howell, 1985, which occurred in late Pliocene localities

672 of Morocco, Tanzania and South Africa (Werdelin and Peigné, 2010), but is absent
673 from LBW. Small musteloids may be absent in Africa during this time because
674 small carnivore niches were occupied by small herpestids and viverrids, which are
675 also very common at LBW, with at least two small taxa for each family (Hendey,
676 1974, Werdelin, 2006; Werdelin and Peigné, 2010).

677

678 **Phylogenetic Analysis**

679 Suprageneric taxonomy can be a critical problem for the fossil taxa due to the
680 fragmentary dental, cranial and postcranial material, and the presence of primitive
681 and derived characters (Valenciano et al., 2017a). The systematics of Mellivorinae
682 and the tribe Mellivorini have been extensively discussed in the past (e.g., Pia,
683 1939; Tobien, 1955; Webb 1969; Ginsburg, 1977; Ginsburg and Morales, 1992;
684 McKenna and Bell, 1997; Ginsburg, 1999; Valenciano et al., 2015, 2017a, 2020a).
685 Pia (1939) used comparative morphology to subdivide the Mellivorinae in the “sub-
686 subfamilies”: Mellivorini (*Mellivora*, *Promellivora* Pilgrim, 1932, and *Eomellivora*
687 Zdansky, 1924), Ischyriactini (*Ischyriactis* Helbing, 1930, *Laphictis* Viret, 1933,
688 *Hadriactis* Pia, 1939, and the North American endemic megalictine *Megalictis*
689 Matthew, 1907, *Aulurocyon* Peterson, 1907, *Oligobunis* Cope, 1881). Later, Tobien
690 (1955) reclassified these groups at the tribe rank and added *Hoplictis helbingi*
691 (Viret, 1951) into Ischyriactini. Webb (1969) introduced several changes to the
692 tribes within Mellivorinae with his final tribes resolved as: (1) Mellivorini
693 (*Mellivora*, *Promellivora*, *Eomellivora*, *Perunium* Orlov, 1948, *Megalictis* and
694 *Aelurocyon*), (2) Gulonini (*Ischyriactis*, *Hadriactis*, *Plesiogulo* Zdansky, 1924 and
695 *Gulo* Pallas, 1780), (3) Brachypsalini (*Brachypsalis* Cope, 1890, *Paroligobunis*
696 Peterson, 1910, *Sthenictis* Peterson, 1910, and *Brachypsaloides* Webb, 1969). New

697 relationships are being assessed using cladistics methods for Miocene mustelids.
698 Thus, Valenciano et al. (2020a) resolved Guloninae as comprised of the tribes
699 Gulonini (*Gulo*, *Plesiogulo* and *Iberictis* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992) and
700 Ischyriictini (*Ischyriictis*, *Laphictis*, and *Dehmictis* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992). In
701 Valenciano et al. (2015, 2017a, 2020a) Mellivorinae includes the genera *Mellivora*,
702 *Eomellivora* (= *Perunium*, and *Hadriictis*), *Ekorus* Werdelin, 2003, *Howellictis*, and
703 possibly *Hoplictis* Ginsburg, 1961. Valenciano et al. (2016), interpreted the North
704 American Oligobuninae as containing among others *Oligobunis*, and *Megalictis*
705 (= *Aelurocyon*, and *Paroligobunis*) (Valenciano et al., 2016).

706 Our cladistics analysis recognizes two main clades: Mellivorinae and
707 Guloninae (Fig. 8). Synapomorphies for each node are reported in Table S5. The
708 relationship of the medium size mustelid *Sthenictis* sp, *Ischyriictis zibethoides* and
709 *Laphictis mustelinus* are not resolved by our phylogenetic analysis. In the previous
710 analysis of Valenciano et al., (2020a) both *I. zibethoides* and *L. mustelinus* were
711 nested with *Dehmictis vorax* in the tribe Ischyriictini, however they appear herein in
712 a polytomy. The primitive morphology of *Sthenictis* sp, *I. zibethoides* and *L.*
713 *mustelinus*, which share several symplesiomorphies, may support their potential
714 Guloninae affinity, therefore we interpreted them as stem Guloninae. The clade
715 Gulonini is very-well supported (Fig. 8). It is located as the sister group of the
716 living *Martes foina-Pekania pennanti*, in agreement with molecular data based
717 phylogenies (Koepfli et al., 2008; Sato et al., 2012; Li et al., 2014; Zhu et al.,
718 2016), where wolverines (*Gulo*) is always closely related to martens (*Martes*) and
719 fisher (*Pekania*). The gulonini show minor differences to the one from Valenciano
720 et al., (2020a). Here, *Plesiogulo monspessulanus* nests with *Gulo* spp., rather with
721 the early Miocene *Iberictis*. This difference in the new phylogeny, stresses the

722 importance of the inclusion of postcranial characters in phylogenies. The
723 incorporation of more postcrania data of the early Miocene *Iberictis*, the middle
724 Miocene *Sthenictis* sp., *I. zibethoides* and *L. mustelinus* and the late Miocene
725 *Plesiogulo* spp., are needed to refine their evolutive relationships. Our phylogenetic
726 analysis suggests a new evolutionary framework in Mellivorinae, which two mains
727 clades, interpreted as a tribe level, are distinguished within this subfamily:
728 Eomellivorini Zdansky, 1924 (new rank) (*Eomellivora* spp. + *Ekorus*) and
729 Mellivorini Gray, 1865 (*Howellictis* + *Mellivora* spp.). We identify for the first
730 time the clade Eomellivorini, defined by the common ancestor of *Eomellivora*
731 *piveteaui* and *Ekorus ekakeran* and all of its descendants. This clade is strongly
732 supported (Fig. 8). It comprises very large mellivorines from the late Miocene of
733 Eurasia, North America, and Africa that are characterized by both primitive
734 dentition—presence of p1 and m2, enlarged M1 styler area—and derived
735 dentition—slender and multicuspid premolars and m1 talonid reduced to a single
736 cuspid placed directly distal to the trigonid blade. The postcranial skeleton includes
737 cursorial adaptations (Werdelin, 2003; Valenciano et al., 2015, 2017b) observed in
738 canids or hyaenids, but not seen in Mustelidae. Some of this traits are a small-size
739 supraepicondilar crest, a distinct reduction in the medial epicondyle, and a sub-
740 quadrangular distal epiphysis of the humerus; ulna with a rectilinear tuber olecrani,
741 and a reduced articular circumference integrated in the styloid process, and lastly an
742 elongated calcaneus with a reduced sustentacular facet and a reduced process for
743 the M. quadratus plantae. Here the tribe Mellivorini encompasses *Mellivora* spp.
744 (*M. benfieldi* + *M. capensis*) plus *H. valentini*. They are small- to medium
745 mellivorines with P4 protocone mesially placed, M1 with a reduced metacone and
746 with a lingual platform enclosed by the protocone, P1-p1 absent, and a robust

747 calcaneal tuber among other traits (Table S5). According to this, *Erokomellivora*
748 and the late Miocene *Promellivora* from the Dhok Pathan in Siwalik, India
749 (Pilgrim, 1932) are likely part of Mellivorini. Eomellivorini is the sister group of
750 the African Mellivorini. It has also been proposed that *Mellivora* probably evolved
751 in the latest Miocene from *Er. lothagamensis*, *H. valentini* or a similar form
752 (Werdelin, 2003; Werdelin and Peigné, 2010; Werdelin and Dehghani, 2011). Our
753 phylogenetic analysis (Fig. 8) suggests *Howellictis* is the sister taxon of *Mellivora*,
754 though more fossils of Mio-Pliocene mellivorines – especially *Erokomellivora* –
755 are necessary to fully resolve the origins of *Mellivora*.

756

757

CONCLUSIONS

758

759 We describe abundant new fossils of *M. benfieldi*, including several
760 hemimandibles, and previously unknown upper dentition C, I3, P3 and P4, as well
761 as remains of the forelimb, and hind limb. These new specimens of *M. benfieldi*
762 expands our knowledge of its intraspecific variability, paleobiology, and
763 distribution in the LBW's members, being reported for the first time in LQSM
764 (SAM-PQL 25606 and 51386). *Mellivora benfieldi* also occurred in the late
765 Miocene of Italy and Ethiopia, and is clearly distinguished from other African
766 mellivorines, such as the middle-late Miocene '*Eomellivora*' *tugenensis* from
767 Ngorora, Kenya, and the late Miocene *Howellictis* from Chad, and *Erokomellivora*
768 from Kenya, and the living honey badger *M. capensis* by the overall morphology
769 and proportions of the dentition and postcranial skeleton. The postcranial remains
770 of *M. benfieldi* indicate semifossorial abilities, similar to those of *M. capensis*. We
771 infer *M. benfieldi* was an opportunistic, medium-sized carnivoran in the carnivore

772 guild of LBW. This is the first cladistics analysis to include these taxa, and a sister-
773 group relationship between *M. benfieldi* and *M. capensis* is confirmed. We create a
774 tribe within Mellivorinae: Eomellivorini (*Eomellivora* spp.+ *Ekorus*) and suggest
775 Mellivorini includes *M. benfieldi*, *M. capensis*, *H. valentini*, *Er. lothagamensis* and
776 the Indian taxon *Promellivora punjabiensis*.

777

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814

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1198
1199 Submitted November 01st, 2019; accepted Month DD, YYYY

1200 FIGURE CAPTIONS

1201
1202 FIGURE 1. Location of the Langebaanweg fossil site. **A**, Silhouette of Africa,
1203 indicating the position of Langebaanweg (gray star); **B**, Simplified geographic map
1204 of South Africa. Modified from Govender (2019). **Abbreviations:** WCFP, West
1205 Coast Fossil Park. [planned for column width]

1206
1207 FIGURE 2. Postcranial measurements used in this work, based on *Mellivora*
1208 *capensis* (ZM-41666 and ZM-41483). Humerus in cranial (**A**), and lateral (**B**)
1209 views; Radius in proximal (**C**), distal (**D**), caudal (**E**), and medial (**F**) views; Ulna
1210 in cranial (**G**), and medial (**H**) views; Metacarpal V in medial (**I**) and dorsal (**J**)
1211 views; Femur in cranial (**K**), proximal (**L**), and distal (**M**) views; Calcaneus in
1212 dorsal (**N**), lateral (**O**), and distal (**P**) views. **Description of the measurements:**
1213 **Humerus.** lateromedial width of the diaphyseal shaft measured at the last third of
1214 the bone, where the lateral crest of *M. anconeus* finish (**1**), height of the medial
1215 epicondyle (**2**), height (**3**) and length (**4**) of the humeral condyle (trochlea +
1216 capitulum), maximum lateromedial width of the distal epiphysis (**5**), craniocaudal

1217 width at the point where measurement 1 was collected (6), and craniocaudal width
1218 of the lateral epicondyle (7); **Radius**. total length (1), lateromedial (2), and
1219 craniocaudal (3) widths of the proximal epiphysis, lateromedial (4) and
1220 craniocaudal (5) widths of the middle point of the diaphysis, lateromedial (6) and
1221 craniocaudal (7) widths of the distal epiphysis; **Ulna**. Total length (1), maximum
1222 lateromedial width of the olecranon tuber (2), maximum craniocaudal width of the
1223 olecranon tuber (3), proximodistal height of the proximal epiphysis of the ulna,
1224 measured from the proximal edge of the olecranon to the distal edge of the radial
1225 notch (4), proximodistal height of the trochlear notch (5), proximodistal height of
1226 the olecranon (6), lateromedial width of the radial notch, comprising both medial
1227 and lateral coronoid processes (7), lateromedial (8) and craniocaudal widths of the
1228 middle point of the diaphysis (9), craniocaudal width of the distal epiphysis at the
1229 level of the articular circumference (10), craniocaudal (11) and lateromedial (12)
1230 widths of the styloid process; **Metacarpal V**. dorsopalmar (1) and lateromedial (2)
1231 widths of the distal epiphysis, total length (3), dorsopalmar (4), and lateromedial (5)
1232 widths of the middle point of the diaphysis, dorsopalmar (6) and lateromedial (7)
1233 widths of the proximal epiphysis; **Femur**. Lateroproximal-mediiodistal width of the
1234 articular head (1), craniocaudal width of the articular head (2), maximum
1235 lateromedial width of the proximal epiphysis (3), lateromedial width of the distal
1236 epiphysis (4), and craniocaudal length of the distal epiphysis (5); **Calcaneus**. Total
1237 length (1), maximum width (2), maximum height (3), proximodistal length of the
1238 articular surface (4), proximodistal (5) and lateromedial (6) widths of the *tuber*
1239 *calcanei*, dorsoplantar (7) and lateromedial (8) lengths of the cuboid facet. [planned
1240 for page width]
1241

1242 FIGURE 3. New dental and mandibular material of *Mellivora benfieldi* from
1243 Langebaanweg (South Africa). **A**. SAM-PQL-72167, right I3 in distal (**A1**), buccal
1244 (**A2**), and mesial (**A3**) views; **B**. SAM-PQL-69620C, left CX in buccal (**B1**), distal
1245 (**B2**), and lingual (**B3**) views; **C**. SAM-PQL-5138B, left CX in buccal (**C1**), distal
1246 (**C2**), and lingual (**C3**) views; **D**. SAM-PQL-50197, right P3 in buccal (**D1**), lingual
1247 (**D2**), and occlusal (**D3**) views; **E**. SAM-PQL-72165, right P3 in buccal (**E1**), and
1248 occlusal (**E2**) views; **F**. SAM-PQL-72227, fragmentary right P4 in buccal (**F1**),
1249 lingual (**F2**), and occlusal (**F3**) views; **G**. SAM-PQL-72174, fragmentary left
1250 hemimandible in buccal (**G1**), lingual (**G2**), occlusal (**G3**) and ventral (**G4**) views;
1251 **H**. SAM-PQL-50444, left p2 in buccal (**H1**), lingual (**H2**), and occlusal (**H3**)
1252 views; **I**. SAM-PQL-69620B, fragmentary left hemimandible in buccal (**I1**), lingual
1253 (**I2**), and occlusal (**I3**) views; **J**. SAM-PQL-50002, fragmentary left hemimandible
1254 in buccal (**J1**), lingual (**J2**), and occlusal (**J3**) views; **K**. SAM-PQL-50105,
1255 fragmentary left hemimandible in buccal (**K1**), and occlusal (**K2**) views; **L**. SAM-
1256 PQL-50106, fragmentary right hemimandible in buccal (**L1**), and occlusal (**L2**)
1257 views. Scale bar equals 2 cm. [planned for page width]

1258

1259 FIGURE 4. New postcranial material of the forelimb of *Mellivora benfieldi* from
1260 Langebaanweg (South Africa). **A-F**. SAM-PQL-72176, left fragmentary humerus
1261 in cranial (**A**), lateral (**B**), caudal (**C**), medial (**D**), distal (**E**), proximal (**F**) views;
1262 **G-K**. SAM-PQL-41875, right fragmentary humerus diaphysis in distal (**G**), rostral
1263 (**H**), lateral (**I**), caudal (**J**), and medial (**K**) views; **L-O**. SAM-PQL-72175, right
1264 ulna in cranial (**L**), medial (**M**), caudal (**N**), and lateral (**O**) views; **P**. SAM-PQL-
1265 25606, right fragmentary ulna in rostral view; **Q**. SAM-PQL-69620A, right
1266 fragmentary ulna in rostral view; **R-W**. SAM-PQL-69620E, right fifth metacarpal

1267 (Mc V) in proximal (**R**), distal (**S**), dorsal (**T**), lateral (**U**), ventral (**V**), and medial
1268 (**W**) views. Scale bar equals 2 cm. [planned for page width]

1269

1270 FIGURE 5. New postcranial material of the hind limb of *Mellivora benfieldi* from
1271 Langebaanweg (South Africa). **A-E**. SAM-PQL-42486, femur, right proximal
1272 epiphysis in rostral (**A**), medial (**B**), caudal (**C**), lateral (**D**), and proximal (**E**)
1273 views; **F-I**. SAM-PQL-41513A, femur, left distal epiphysis (belonging to the same
1274 specimen than SAM-PQL-42486) in rostral (**F**), medial (**G**), caudal (**H**), and distal
1275 (**I**) views; **J-O**. SAM-PQL-69634, right calcaneum in dorsal (**J**), medial (**K**),
1276 plantar (**L**), lateral (**M**), proximal (**N**), and distal (**O**) views. Scale bar equals 2 cm.
1277 [planned for page width]

1278

1279 FIGURE 6. Measurements (mm) of the lower carnassial (m1) of African and
1280 Eurasian mellivorines as depicted in bivariate plots of maximum mesiodistal length
1281 (L) vs. maximum buccolingual width (W). Sources: Hendeby, 1974; Rook et al.,
1282 1991; Geraads, 1997; Werdelin, 2003; Bonis et al., 2009; Haile-Selassie and
1283 Howell, 2009; Geraads, 2016, and this work. [planned for page width]

1284

1285 FIGURE 7. Main comparative material of mellivorines from Africa herein
1286 analyzed. **A-C**. SAM-PQL-42838, holotype of *Mellivora benfieldi* from
1287 Langebaanweg described by Hendeby (1978a), fragmentary right hemimandible in
1288 buccal (**A**), lingual (**B**), and occlusal (**C**) views; **D-F**. SAM-PQL-50443, *Mellivora*
1289 *benfieldi* from Langebaanweg described by Hendeby (1978a), fragmentary right
1290 hemimandible in buccal (**D**), lingual (**E**), and occlusal (**F**) views; **G-I**. KNM-LT
1291 23926, *Erokomellivora lothagamensis* Lothagam, upper member of the Nawata

1292 Formation, Kenya, Late Miocene, fragmentary left hemimandible in buccal (**G**),
1293 lingual (**H**), and occlusal (**I**) views; **J-L**. SAM-ZM-41666, *Mellivora capensis*,
1294 living honey badger, left hemimandible in buccal (**J**), lingual (**K**), and occlusal (**L**)
1295 views. Scale bar equals 2 cm. [planned for page width]

1296

1297 FIGURE 8. Phylogenetic relationships of *Mellivora benfieldi* within selected
1298 Mustelidae. Bootstrap 50% majority-rule consensus (length 249 steps; consistency
1299 index (CI) = 0.4458, homoplasy index (HI) = 0.5542, and retention index (RI) =
1300 0.6434) was obtained using PAUP*4.0b10 (Swofford, 2002). The outgroup is
1301 *Zodiolestes daimonelixensis*. The numbers below nodes are Bremer support, and
1302 the numbers above nodes are Bootstrap support percentages (only shown if ≥ 50).
1303 Letters (A-E) indicated selected nodes. The synapomorphies for each node are
1304 reported in Table S5. [planned for column width]

1305

1306

final word count: 13377

A

LBW
(WCFP)

B

Saldanha

★ LBW (WCFP)

Langebaan

Atlantic Ocean

Cape Town

N

100 km

▲ *Howellictis valentini*, TM 192 Toros Menalla (Chad), late Miocene (c.a., 7 Ma)

■ *Erokomellivora lothagamensis*, Lothagam, upper member of the Nawata Fm., (Kenya), late Miocene (6.5–5.5 Ma)

● *Mellivora benfieldi*, Langebaanweg (South Africa), early Pliocene (c.a., 5.2 Ma)

● *Mellivora benfieldi*, Brisighella (Italy), late Miocene (MN13, c.a., 6 Ma)

○ *Mellivora aff. benfieldi*, Middle Awash (Ethiopia), late Miocene (c.a., 6–5.5 Ma)

■ *Mellivora cf. capensis*, Ahl al Oughlam (Morocco), late Pliocene (c.a., 2.5 Ma)

◇ *Mellivora capensis*, Tighennif (Algeria), Pleistocene (late Calabrian 1.8–0.78 Ma)

* *Mellivora capensis*, Elandsfontein (South Africa), Pleistocene (1–0.6 Ma)

■ *Mellivora capensis*, Living sample (n=20)

TABLE 1. Upper teeth measurements (in mm) of the new specimens of *Mellivora benfieldi* from Langebaanweg.

Taxa	I3		CX		P3		P4	
<i>Mellivora</i>								
<i>benfieldi</i>	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W
SAM-PQL-72167	6.7	4.7	—	—	—	—	—	—
SAM-PQL-69620C	—	—	8.5	6.5	—	—	—	—
SAM-PQL-51386	—	—	7.0	5.4	—	—	—	—
SAM-PQL-72165	—	—	—	—	8.0	4.8	—	—
SAM-PQL-50107	—	—	—	—	7.2	4.1	—	—
SAM-PQL-72227	—	—	—	—	—	—	12.6	—

SAM-

PQL- — — — — — — 9.7 5.3 14.2 6.2 5.0 — —

6385*

SAM-

PQL- 6.6 5.3 4.9 3.4 6.4 4.4 8.5 4.8 11.7 5.2 4.5 — —

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